

AC Breakdown Voltage of Fe₃O₄ based Nanodielectric Fluids- Part 2: Analysis of Fluids with High Moisture Content

Víctor A. Primo, Belén García, Juan Carlos Burgos and Daniel Pérez

Department of Electrical Engineering,
Universidad Carlos III de Madrid,
Avda de la Universidad, 20
28911, Leganés, Madrid, Spain

ABSTRACT

Several authors have suggested that one of the main difference between conventional insulating liquids and nanodielectric fluids is the behavior of the water in the nanodielectric fluid. It has been reported that the impact of water on the dielectric strength is reduced when nanoparticles are dispersed in the fluid, and that nanodielectric fluids present higher breakdown voltage values than the base liquids under similar moisture content. The second part of this two-part paper analyzes the effect of the presence of water on the AC breakdown voltage of several nanodielectric fluids prepared from mineral oil and Fe₃O₄ nanoparticles in different concentrations. The fluids were conditioned to a range of moisture content and tested under different conditions. An exhaustive measuring campaign was carried out that was completed with a non-parametric and a parametric statistical analysis of the results. As will be shown in the paper, an increase on the solubility of nanodielectric fluids has been observed which is related with the enhancement of the breakdown voltage of these liquids. The evolution of the breakdown voltage was analyzed both for fluids with similar absolute moisture contents and also for fluids with similar relative saturation conditions.

Index Terms —dielectric Liquids, nanotechnology, nanodielectric fluids, dielectric breakdown, Weibull distribution

1 INTRODUCTION

WATER has a negative impact on some of the dielectric properties of insulating fluids. The presence of water and particles are the two main factors that determine the value of the breakdown voltage (BV) of a dielectric oil [1-2]. Miners [2] reported a reduction of the BV of 25 % of mineral oil (MO) when the water content increases from 5 to 20 ppm. Water have also an important role in the BV of natural and synthetic esters, although absolute moisture contents above 100 ppm are admitted in those fluids without a significant reduction of their BV [1].

The reason for the worsening of the fluid's BV is that in presence of an electric field, water molecules tend to migrate towards regions with higher field solicitations, forming conductive paths that facilitate the dielectric breakdown [3-4].

Several authors have presented experimental studies proving that the dispersion of nanoparticles (NP) in dielectric fluids can lead to an improvement of the dielectric properties of the base liquids [5-8]. In particular, a number of studies dealing with the breakdown voltage at 50 Hz (AC BV) and the breakdown voltage under impulses have been published in the last years [9-10]. Most authors relate the observed improvements with the reduction of mobility of the free charges present in NDF caused by the

interaction between these charges and the NP. The interaction has been described either as a bonding between charges and NP [11] and also as a trapping and de-trapping process in shallow traps [12].

Also, recent works have reported that the impact of the water dissolved in the Nano Dielectric Fluids (NDF) on the AC BV is smaller than on the base fluids [13-17]. The explanation given to this improvement is related with the interaction between the NP and the water molecules dissolved in the fluids. It has been suggested that the bounding between water molecules and the NP limits their mobility and makes more difficult the formation of conductive paths [18].

Weijun Yin reported that, in a MO-based NDF containing Al₂O₃ NP, the AC BV decreased with increasing water content, but a much greater water content was required in samples containing NP to produce a comparable decrease in AC-BV, relative to samples without NP[17]. Improvements above 100 % are shown by this author when the AC BV of the NDF and the base fluid are compared for simmilar moisture contents [17].

Jin [19] compared the AC-BV of MO and a MO-based SiO₂ NDF with NP concentrations 0.01 and 0.02 vol. % and moisture contents 15 and 25 ppm. She reported increases of the AC-BV within 10 and 25 % when comparing the NDF with the MO at

similar water contents. The same author compared the AC-BV of the NDF silica NP, which are hydrophilic, with that of another NDF that containing silica NP modified with the surfactant silane coupling agent Z6011, which renders them hydrophobic. She found that the AC-BV of the latter NDF were similar to that of the base fluid, whereas the AC-BV of the NDF containing hydrophilic silica NP was 10-25 % greater than that of the base fluid. She explained this finding by the fact that the water molecules bound to the surfaces of hydrophilic NP but do not link to those surfaces when the NP are hydrophobic.

Segal [15] also investigated the impact of water on the AC BV of a Fe_3O_4 based NDF with moisture content above 25 ppm reporting an increase of 43%.

Although at the moment consensus exists on the fact that the presence of NP influences the behaviour of the water molecules in NDF, what have an effect in the BV of these liquids, the topic is still under research and more work is necessary to assess the performance of the NDF under a wider range of scenarios.

The present paper studies the influence of water on the AC BV of several MO based NDF. The fluids under study were prepared with several concentrations of conductive Fe_3O_4 NP and were subjected to different conditioning processes to obtain NDF with a range of moisture contents.

The measurements were analysed from two different perspectives; first the dependence of the AC BV of the different liquids with the absolute moisture was studied, as was typically done by other authors. Additionally, a characterization of the solubility curve of the fluids under study suggested us that it was necessary to carry out an additional analysis to determine how the AC BV depends on the relative saturations (RS) of the NDF. The analysis of the results was carried out using both Weibull and Normal distribution and non-parametric statistical analysis. Finally, a discussion is included in the paper aimed at explaining the processes and physical mechanisms that can justify the improvement of the dielectric properties of NDF when high amounts of water are dissolved in the fluids.

2 SAMPLE CONDITIONING AND MOISTURE MEASUREMENTS

2.1 SAMPLE CONDITIONING

The objective of the second part of this work is to evaluate how the AC BV of different NDF is affected by the moisture content of the liquids.

Dry samples of NDF with different concentrations of NP were subjected to conditioning processes aimed at obtaining samples with different moisture contents. Fluids with RS 25% and 50% were prepared. The AC BV obtained on these samples were compared with those obtained on dry samples, which were the ones analyzed in the first part of this work [20].

To obtain fluids with RS 25%, samples of MO and NDF with NP concentrations 0.05, 0.1 and 0.2 g/L were kept at room conditions in the laboratory for at least 72 hours. The temperature and relative humidity in the laboratory were stable at values 20 °C and 25%, respectively.

Samples with RS 50 % were obtained by keeping the samples in an environmental chamber until reaching steady state condition. Periodical sampling and testing were carried out

finding that about 72 hours were necessary to reach equilibrium conditions at temperature 30 °C and relative humidity 50 %.

It was ascertained that all the samples had reached steady state condition by the end of the conditioning process.

2.2 MOISTURE MEASUREMENTS

Karl Fischer (KF) titration [21] is generally applied to determine the absolute moisture content of transformer oils in the lab. The methodology that is commonly applied to characterize the moisture content of a liquid samples cannot be applied when measuring the water content of NDF, because the presence of conductive NP in the titration vessel would affect to the currents measured in the KF equipment currents leading to wrong results. Alternatively, an oven can be used to heat the sample of the fluid under test, evaporating the water contained in it and driving the water to the titration vessel to be quantified.

In this work, the water content was measured using a KF Coulometer (Methrom 831) combined with a Karl-Fischer 860. The measuring procedure consisted of filling a 2mL sample of the fluid that is being evaluated in a vial. The vial is fitted in the oven where it is heated up to 110°C.

Table 1 shows the absolute moisture content of the samples of MO and NDF included in the study measured after the manufacturing and conditioning processes. It must be noted that for each considered NP concentration (0.05, 0.1 and 0.2 g/L), two samples with three different moisture contents were prepared (dry, RS 25% and RS 50%). The values presented in Table 1 are the results of the two moisture determinations performed two independent samples and the mean values of the two measurements.

The moisture contents measured for each fluid at the end of the conditioning processes and the corresponding tendency lines are plotted in Figure 2. Using the solubility curve provided by the manufacturer of the MO it was estimated that the RS for the dry condition was about a 10%. As can be seen, all the NDF present higher moisture contents than the MO for every conditioned process. Additionally, as the concentration of NP in the fluid increases, the moisture contents obtained for the same conditioning process grow.

Figure 1. Karl Fischer coulometric titrator with evaporation oven.

The result suggests that the solubility of the NDF under analysis is higher than that of the base fluid and that the solubility rises as higher masses of NP are dispersed in the base fluid. It must be remarked that the conditions applied during the

conditioning process were identical for all fluids under test, and thus the RS of the resulting fluids was the same too. A similar behavior was observed by the authors in a previous work on a natural-ester based NDF [22].

Table 1. Moisture content of samples after conditioning.

		Moisture content (ppm)		
		Dry	RS 25%	RS 50%
MO	M1	7.53	15.82	39.15
	M2	8.67	19.41	39.45
	Mean	8.10	17.62	39.30
NDF 0.05 g/L	M1	9.55	24.46	45.86
	M2	13.67	30.34	54.26
	Mean	11.61	27.40	50.06
NDF 0.1 g/L	M1	12.73	27.00	54.95
	M2	16.31	30.44	55.55
	Mean	14.52	28.72	55.25
NDF 0.2 g/L	M1	13.51	31.96	60.75
	M2	19.81	32.98	66.41
	Mean	16.66	32.47	63.58

The rise of the solubility may be due to the fact that the NP are able to bound water molecules increasing the amount of water that can be dissolved in the fluids under similar conditions. As will be shown later, this fact has a positive impact on the dielectric properties of the NDF.

3 AC BREAKDOWN VOLTAGE TESTS

Authors who have previously worked in the topic of water and NDF compare the breakdown strength of the base fluids and the NDF under similar absolute moisture contents [13], [17]. Considering that the solubility of NDFs becomes higher as the concentration of NP dispersed in them rises it seems clear that it is also important to compare the AC BV of NDF and MO under similar RS conditions.

Figure 2. Moisture content of the NDF and the MO vs relative saturation of the samples.

In the following subsections the influence of the moisture content of the fluids on their AC BV is analyzed. The dependence of the dielectric strength of the samples with the absolute moisture is analyzed first; then the analysis is repeated

considering the evolution of the AC BV with the RS of the fluids.

3.1 MEASURING PROCEDURE

The AC BV of the different samples of MO and NDF was characterized following the experimental procedure described in [20]. All the NDF under test were analyzed by duplicate, recording 20 breakdowns on two fresh samples. Thereby, at the end of the testing period, 40 breakdown values were available for each NDF at each considered moisture content.

The evolution of the moisture content of the samples was monitored throughout the AC BV testing. Moisture measurements were performed on each fluid sample before starting the AC BV tests and after the 10th breakdown. Then, four moisture measurements were available for each analyzed fluid and moisture content.

3.2 EVOLUTION OF THE AC BV WITH THE ABSOLUTE MOISTURE OF THE SAMPLES

Figure 3 shows the AC BV vs the absolute moisture content of the fluid's samples for all the samples included in the study including a tendency line for each fluid. A Boltzman model was considered to find the adjustment curves in agreement with the recommendation of CIGRE WG D1.52 [23].

Looking at the experimental data in Figure 3, it can be seen that at very low moisture contents all the analyzed fluids show AC BV values within 90 and 100 kV; then, as the moisture content of the fluids rises, the AC BV of all the fluids drops although not all of them worsen their properties at the same rate. In this sense, for moisture contents around 20 ppm the AC BV of the MO drops to values near 60 kV while the AC BV of the NDF with NP concentration 0.2 g/L is still around 100 kV and remains close to 70 kV when the moisture content rises up to

Figure 3. Measurements of AC Breakdown Voltage at 50 Hz vs moisture content measured on the samples and tendency lines.

40 ppm. At very high moisture contents the AC BV of all the fluids drops to values near 25 kV, but while in the MO these values were recorded at moisture contents around 40 ppm, in the NDF these values correspond to moisture contents above 60 ppm.

Table 2 shows the AC BV for different moisture contents for the analyzed NDF. These data have been derived from the tendency lines shown in Figure 3. As can be seen all the NDF have higher values of the AC BV than the MO at similar moisture contents. This is especially noticeable for the NDF with NP concentration 0.2 g/L, which present values within a 30 and a 100 % higher than those of the MO. These results are in agreement with those shown by other authors [13], [15]–[17] in previous works.

Table 2. AC BV (kV) of the MO and the NDF vs absolute water content (ppm) of the sample.

Moisture Content	MO	NDF 0.05 g/L	NDF 0.1 g/L	NDF 0.2 g/L
10 ppm	87.4	92.4	93.8	>98.6
20 ppm	66.9	75.6	74.9	86.8
30 ppm	48.0	56.2	57.5	70.0
40 ppm	31.1	40.7	42.0	55.0
50 ppm	16.6	27.3	28.6	42.0
60 ppm	<15	16.0	17.3	31.1

3.3 EVOLUTION OF THE AC BV WITH THE RELATIVE SATURATION OF THE SAMPLES

Table 3 shows the mean value of the AC BV values of the four analyzed fluids when they were conditioned to RS 25%. As can be seen, the mean and the median values are only improved slightly by the presence of NP for the case of the maximum concentration studied (0.2 g/L), while for 0.05 g/L and 0.1 g/L, there is a worsening of these values.

An analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed which shown that there are significative statistical differences between the means of the four groups (p -value= $9.94 \cdot 10^{-5}$, $F= 7.51$), although the further Tukey HSD test shown that the only populations that differ are the NDF with NP concentrations 0.1 g/L and 0.2 g/L, while no NDF have a mean value significantly different from MO (Figure 4).

On the other hand, a significant reduction of the standard deviation is appreciated for all NP concentrations. There is also a very clear improvement in the lowest AC BV recorded values (characterized by means of percentile 2).

Table 3. Statistical of the AC BV values measured on samples of MO and NDF with RS 25%.

AC BV	MO	NDF 0.05 g/L	NDF 0.1 g/L	NDF 0.2 g/L
Mean (kV)	64.55	60.55	58.46	70.85
Std dv	17.22	6.80	12.95	11.04
Percentile 2 (kV)	27.94	41.04	36.10	41.56
Percent. 50 (kV)	63.05	61.85	59.45	71.20
Percent. 90 (kV)	87.15	67.85	75.00	85.50

The distribution of AC BV along the tests is shown in Figure 5. As can be shown in Figure 5 the minimum values of the ACBV are higher for NFD than for MO what is an important advantage in transformer design.

Figure 4: Multiple comparison of the means of the AC BV of the NDF and the AC BV of MO with RS 25%

Figure 5. Frequency of ACBV for each fluid at 25% RS for MO and NDF with NP concentration 0.2 g/L.

The data of the AC BV measurements on fluid samples conditioned to a RS 25% were fitted to Weibull (Figure 6) and Normal distributions giving similar results. The Shapiro-Wilk test was performed and in most of the cases the null hypothesis

Figure 6. Weibull Breakdown Probability for AC BV (50 Hz) with 25% RS.

was accepted (significance level 0.05), indicating that the population is normally distributed in all of the cases except for the AC BV of the NDF with concentrations 0.05 g/L.

Table 4 shows the breakdown voltages calculated according to Weibull and Normal distributions for failure probabilities within 5 and 75 % for the different fluids included in the study. As can be seen a certain improvement of the AC BV is observed on most failure probabilities for the samples with NP concentration 0.2 g/L and a very clear improvement is obtained for the lower failure probabilities for all the analyzed fluids.

Table 4. AC BV (kV) for different failure probabilities according to Weibull and Normal distribution. Fluids conditioned with RS 25%

Fail Prob	AC BV (kV)							
	MO		NDF 0.05 g/L		NDF 0.1 g/L		NDF 0.2 g/L	
	W	N	W	N	W	N	W	N
5%	36.2	36.5	51.8	53.4	34.5	35.8	52.5	54.8
10%	43.3	43.6	54.4	55.4	40.3	40.6	57.1	58.3
25%	55.5	55.5	58.5	58.5	48.7	48.7	64.1	64.2
50%	68.9	68.6	62.4	62.1	58.0	57.6	71.1	70.6
75%	81.7	81.7	65.6	65.6	66.5	66.5	77.0	77.0

The same analysis was repeated for the samples prepared with RS 50%. Table 5 shows the statistical analysis of the measurements. As can be seen, the values of the mean and the median of the AC BV were very similar to those of the MO although an improvement is appreciated in the standard deviation of the data. As for the samples conditioned with RS 25%, again the percentiles study shows that the addition of NP to the MO tends to improve the lower breakdown voltages, although the variation is small in most cases.

Table 5. Statistical of the AC BV values measured on samples of MO and NDF with RS 50%.

AC BV	MO	NDF 0.05 g/L	NDF 0.1 g/L	NDF 0.2 g/L
Mean (kV)	29.38	28.16	26.00	28.95
Std dv	7.69	4.00	4.40	4.55
Percentile 2 (kV)	19.21	20.02	17.16	21.14
Percent. 50 (kV)	27.40	28.05	25.50	28.70
Percent. 90 (kV)	37.75	34.40	31.90	36.30

In this case, the ANOVA analysis showed that there are statistical differences between the means of the four groups (p -value= 0.0271, F = 3.14), and the Tukey HSD test showed that the NDF with NP concentrations 0.1 g/L is the only fluid that behaves differently from MO (Figure 7).

Figure 8 compares the histograms of the AC BV measurements taken on samples of MO and NDF with NP concentration 0.2 g/L conditioned to RS 50%. As can be seen two breakdowns were recorded at values above 40 kV on samples of MO. However, excluding these two breakdowns, the performance of the NDF is better and the measures present less dispersion.

The fitting of the data to a Weibull distribution are shown in Figure 9 and Table 6. As can be seen these confirm the tendencies observed in the non-parametric analysis: the lowest values of the AC BV increased very slightly for the NDF with NP concentration 0.2 g/L but the difference is not very noticeable. The Shapiro-Wilk test was performed and in most

Figure 7: Multiple comparison of the means of the AC BV of the NDF and the AC BV of MO with RS 50%

Figure 8. Frequency of AC BV for MO and NDF with NP concentration 0.2 g/L RS 50%.

Figure 9. Weibull Probability for AC BV (50 Hz) of fluids with RS 50%.

of the cases the null hypothesis was accepted (significance level 0.05), indicating that the population is normally distributed in all of the cases except for the AC BV of the MO.

Table 6. AC BV (kV) for different failure probabilities according to Weibull and Normal distribution. Fluids conditioned with RS 50%

Fail Prob	AC BV (kV)							
	MO		NDF 0.05 g/L		NDF 0.1 g/L		NDF 0.2 g/L	
	W	N	W	N	W	N	W	N
5%	19.2	20.1	20.0	20.9	19.2	20.1	21.2	22.2
10%	21.5	22.0	21.9	22.5	21.0	21.5	23.1	23.6
25%	25.1	25.1	25.0	25.0	23.7	23.7	25.9	25.8
50%	28.8	28.6	28.0	27.8	26.5	26.3	28.6	28.3
75%	32.0	32.0	30.6	30.6	28.8	28.8	31.0	30.9

4 DISCUSSION

The improvement observed in AC BV of NDF vs. MO with similar RS are not very significant. Table 7 summarizes the percentage of improvement of the main statistical parameters of the AC BV measurements of the NDF with NP concentration 0.2 g/L and those of the MO for different RS of the fluids. For high failure probabilities (F25, F50 and F75 in table 7) data were obtained from the Weibull fitting curve. As the data fitting to the curves in the low region of the curve is poor, for low values of voltage the Percentile 2 of the experimental data is shown.

Table 7. Percentage of improvement (%) of the AC BV parameters of the NDF with NP concentration 0.02 g/L with regard to MO.

RS	Mean	Median	SD	Per2	F25	F50	F75
Dry	9.4	10.3	-36.5	13.3	6.9	9.9	12
25%	9.8	12.9	-35.9	48	15.5	3.2	-5.7
50%	-1.4	4.7	-40.8	10	3.19	-0.7	-3.1

Figure 10 shows the histograms of the AC BV measurements on those two fluids. As can be seen AC BV shift towards lower values as the RS of the fluids increases.

Taking into account the higher water solubility in NDF compared with water solubility in MO the AC BV of the NDF increases dramatically if the measures obtained on NDFs and on MO with similar absolute moisture contents (i.e. ppm of water) are compared. Table 8 summarizes the improvement in % of the AC BV of the NDF prepared with NP concentration 0.2 g/L with respect to that of the MO. This fluid was the one that achieved the best performance for both low and high humidity levels. As can be seen the improvement of the AC BV is between 30 and 150% depending on the considered moisture content.

This result is in agreement with the data provided by other authors on several NDF prepared with MO as base fluids. In this sense Segal [15] reports an increase of 43% for a Fe₃O₄ based NDF with moisture content above 25 ppm, Zhou an increase of 190 % on a TiO₂ based NDF with moisture content 45 ppm and Jin [13] reports an improvement of 25% on a NDF with SiO₂ NP with a moisture content 25 ppm. Weijun Yin [17] reports higher improvements on an Al₂O₃ based NDF, although the NP concentration considered by this author were much higher than the ones considered in this work.

Figure 10: Histogram of the AC BV of MO and the NDF with NP concentration 0.2 g/L for different RS conditions.

Table 8. Percentage of improvement of the AC BV of the NDF with NP concentration 0.2 g/L with regard to that of MO vs. Absolute Moisture.

Abs. Moisture	Increase AC BV NDF 0.2 g/L vs. MO
10 ppm	>13 %
20 ppm	29 %
30 ppm	46 %
40 ppm	77 %
50 ppm	>150 %
60 ppm	>150 %

The explanation that has been generally given to the comparatively smaller impact of moisture on the AC BV of NDF is that the water molecules dissolved in the fluids bond to the NP forming clusters around them [16]. The mobility of the water molecules would therefore decrease, and then, although the presence of larger amounts of water would still reduce the AC BV of these fluids, the reduction is smaller in the presence of the NP [13]. The formation of these clusters has been experimentally demonstrated by Du [18] who measured the spatial charge on MO and NDF with growing water contents. A reduction of the space charge and a more homogenous field distribution was observed in the NDF compared with those in the MO with similar moisture contents.

As can be seen when comparing the performance of the NDF with that of the MO for the same RS the improvement is not

very sharp. Nevertheless if the comparison is made for the same ppm the improvement is significant.

The enhancement of the AC BV observed for NDF when compared with the values measured in MO with similar absolute moisture contents is related with the increase of the solubility of these liquids. In this sense, although the fluids that are compared in Table 7 have the same absolute moisture contents, they are not working under the same RS conditions. This finding is similar to that obtained when comparing MO with natural esters, where the AC BV remains within acceptable limits even with the moisture contents are as high as 400 ppm; however if the evolution of the AC BV with the RS is analyzed the performance is similar to that of MO [9], [25-31].

In the case of the NDF the increase of the solubility and the enhancement of the AC BV are related with the fact that the water molecules in the fluid bond to the NP preventing them from moving freely acting like charge carriers.

When MO and NDF with similar RS conditions are compared, the observed increases of the AC BV are similar to those observed on dry fluids [20] being these enhancements more related with the effect of the NP on the electron transport processes than with the interaction between the water molecules and the NP.

To complete the work and clarify the role of the materials present in the NP suspension MFR-DP1 (which was added to the MO to produce the NDF under test) in the increase of solubility observed in the analyzed NDF, an additional set of solubility measurements was carried out on NDF containing exclusively MO and NP.

Fe₃O₄ NP were dispersed in the MO Nynas Nytro up to concentrations 0.1 and 0.2 g/L. The preparation of these fluids was performed by the company Magnacol U.K. The resulting NDFs were less stable in the long term but it did not show any signs of deposits or precipitation during the testing time. The fluids were subjected the conditioning process explained in section 2.1 and the steady state moisture contents were measured for all the cases. The results of these tests are shown in table 9 together with the results on MO and on the NDF prepared from the NP suspension MFR-DP1.

Table 9. Influence of the solvent and surfactant on the moisture solubility.

Material	Conditioning process		
	Dry	RS 25 %	RS 50%
MO	8.10	17.62	39.30
Nynas + MFR-DP1 0.1g/L	14.52	28.72	55.25
Nynas + NP 0.1 g/L	15.01	26.47	57.32
Nynas + MFR-DP1 0.2g/L	16.66	32.47	63.58
Nynas + NP 0.2 g/L	18,87	37,43	70,51

As can be seen the behavior of both NDF is very similar and the increase in solubility with the concentration of NP can be clearly appreciated in both of them. This suggest that there is no significative influence of the solvent and the surfactant in the measurements and that the reported changes in solubility are related to NP.

5 CONCLUSIONS

In this work an experimental study has been carried out aimed at analyzing the effect of the water in the AC BV of MO and Fe₃O₄ NDF.

It has been shown that the presence of moisture has a negative impact in the NDF and in the MO, although the extent to what the amount of water affects the AC BV of the NDF is lower. This is clearly observed when the BV is obtained as a function of the absolute moisture content of the samples. Improvement up to 150% have been found when comparing the AC BV of NDF and MO for similar absolute moisture contents. These results are in agreement with the observations of other authors, although the study presented in this work considers a wider range of scenarios of moisture contents and types of NDF.

In addition, it has been found that the presence of NP increases the solubility of water in the oil and that this increase is clearly related with the enhancement of the AC BV observed in NDF.

The solubility increase of NDF could have positive effects in the oil-cellulose system such as the displacement of the moisture equilibrium towards the oil, allowing the cellulose insulation to operate dryer. More research is necessary to fully understand the interaction between NDF and cellulosic insulation in the future and to make possible the use of these new type of fluids in transformers.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work has been supported by the Spanish Ministry of Economy and Competitiveness within the project DPI2015-71219-C2-2-R.

REFERENCES

- [1] I. Power and E. Society, "IEEE Guide for Acceptance and Maintenance of Insulating Mineral Oil in Electrical Equipment," vol. 2015, no. June, 2015.
- [2] K. Miners, "PARTICLES AND MOISTURE EFFECT ON DIELECTRIC STRENGTH OF TRANSFORMER OIL," *Trans. Power Appar. Syst.*, no. 3, pp. 751–756, 1982.
- [3] IEC Standard 60422, "Mineral Insulating Oils in Electrical Equipment- Supervision and Maintenance Guidance," 2013.
- [4] A. Abu-Siada, *Power Transformer Condition Monitoring and Diagnosis*, The Instit. 2018.
- [5] W. Sima, J. Shi, Q. Yang, S. Huang, and X. Cao, "Effects of conductivity and permittivity of nanoparticle on transformer oil insulation performance: Experiment and theory," *IEEE Trans. Dielectr. Electr. Insul.*, vol. 22, no. 1, pp. 380–390, 2015.
- [6] Y. Lv, Y. Zhou, C. Li, Q. Wang, and B. Qi, "Recent progress in nanofluids based on transformer oil: Preparation and electrical insulation properties," *IEEE Electr. Insul. Mag.*, vol. 30, no. 5, pp. 23–32, 2014.
- [7] R. Liu, L. A. A. Pettersson, T. Auletta, and O. Hjortstam, "Fundamental research on the application of nano dielectrics to transformers," *Annu. Rep. - Conf. Electr. Insul. Dielectr. Phenomena, CEIDP*, pp. 423–427, 2011.
- [8] V. A. Primo, B. Garcia, and R. Albarraeín, "Improvement of Transformer Liquid Insulation Using Nanodielectric Fluids: A Review," *IEEE Electr. Insul. Mag.*, vol. 34, no. 3, pp. 13–26, 2018.
- [9] M. G. Danikas, A. Bakandritsos, G. D. Peppas, V. P. Charalampakos, E. C. Pyrgioti, and I. F. Gonos, "Statistical investigation of AC breakdown voltage of nanofluids compared with mineral and natural ester oil," *IET Sci. Meas. Technol.*, vol. 10, no. 6, pp. 644–652, 2016.
- [10] U. Khaled and A. Beroual, "AC Dielectric Strength of Synthetic Ester-Based Fe₃O₄, Al₂O₃ and SiO₂ Nanofluids – Conformity

- with Normal and Weibull Distributions,” *IEEE Trans. Dielectr. Electr. Insul.*, vol. 26, no. 2, pp. 625–633, 2019.
- [11] F. M. O’Sullivan, “A model for the initiation and propagation of electrical streamers in transformer oil and transformer oil based nanofluids,” *Thesis (Ph. D.)--Massachusetts Inst. Technol. Dept. Electr. Eng. Comput. Sci.* 2007., p. 309, 2007.
- [12] C. Li, “Effect of electron shallow trap on breakdown performance of transformer oil- based nanofluids,” *J. Appl. Phys.*, no. December 2014, 2011.
- [13] H. Jin, “Dielectric Strength and Thermal Conductivity of Mineral Oil based Nanofluids,” Thesis of Delft University of Technology, the Netherlands, 2015.
- [14] W. Yu, D. M. France, S. U. S. Choi, and J. L. Routbort, “Review and Assessment of Nanofluid Technology for Transportation and Other Applications,” *Energy Syst. Div. Argonne Natl. Lab. Work*, 2007.
- [15] V. Segal, A. Hjortsberg, A. Rabinovich, D. Natrass, and K. Raj, “AC (60 Hz) and impulse breakdown strength of a colloidal fluid based on transformer oil and magnetite nanoparticles,” in *Conference Record of the 1998 IEEE International Symposium on Electrical Insulation (Cat. No.98CH36239)*, 1998, vol. 2, pp. 619–622.
- [16] Y. Zhou *et al.*, “Statistical analysis of moisture ’ s effect on AC breakdown strength of TiO 2 nano fl uids,” *J. Mollecular Liq.*, vol. 249, pp. 420–428, 2018.
- [17] N. Weijun Yin, “Nano Dielectricfluids Pub. No.: US 2013/0285781 A1,” 2013.
- [18] Y. Du *et al.*, “Effect of water adsorption at nanoparticle – oil interface on charge transport in high humidity transformer oil-based nanofluid,” *Colloids Surfaces A Physicochem. Eng. Asp.*, vol. 415, pp. 153–158, 2012.
- [19] H. Jin, T. Andritsch, I. A. Tsekmes, R. Kochetov, P. H. F. Morshuis, and J. J. Smit, “Properties of mineral oil based silica nanofluids,” *IEEE Trans. Dielectr. Electr. Insul.*, vol. 21, no. 3, pp. 1100–1108, 2014.
- [20] V. A. Primo, D. Pérez, B. García, and J. C. Burgos, “AC Breakdown Voltage of Fe 3 O 4 based Nanodielectric Fluids . Part I : Analysis of dry fluids,” *Trans. Dielectr. Electr. Insul.*, no. Under Review.
- [21] Commission International Electrotechnical, “IEC 60814:1997; Insulating liquids – Oil-impregnated paper and pressboard – Determination of water by automatic coulometric Karl Fischer titration Numéro,” 1997.
- [22] D. Pérez, V. Primo, B. García, and J. C. Burgos, “Analysis of Water Solubility in natural-ester based nanodielectric fluids .,” in *IEEE International Conference on Dielectrics*, 2019.
- [23] I. Atanasova-höhlein *et al.*, “Experience with Capacitive On-Line Sensors for Moisture Evaluation in Transformer Insulation,” *IEEE Electr. Insul. Mag.*, no. 1, pp. 18–26, 2019.
- [24] A. Raymon, S. Sakthibalan, C. Cinthal, R. Subramaniraja, and M. Yuvaraj, “Enhancement and comparison of nano-ester insulating fluids,” *IEEE Trans. Dielectr. Electr. Insul.*, vol. 23, no. 2, pp. 892–900, 2016.
- [25] J. Li, R. Liao, and L. Yang, “Investigation of natural ester based liquid dielectrics and nanofluids,” *ICHVE 2012 - 2012 Int. Conf. High Volt. Eng. Appl.*, vol. 56, no. 2 mm, pp. 16–21, 2012.
- [26] Y. Zhong *et al.*, “Insulating properties and charge characteristics of natural ester fluid modified by TiO2 semiconductive nanoparticles,” *IEEE Trans. Dielectr. Electr. Insul.*, vol. 20, no. 1, pp. 135–140, 2013.
- [27] G. Dombek, Z. Nadolny, and P. Przybyłek, “The Study of Thermal Properties of Mineral Oil and Synthetic Ester Modified by Nanoparticles TiO 2 and C 60,” *Ichve*, pp. 1–4, 2014.
- [28] G. D. Peppas *et al.*, “Ultrastable Natural Ester-Based Nanofluids for High Voltage Insulation Applications,” *ACS Appl. Mater. Interfaces*, vol. 8, no. 38, pp. 25202–25209, Sep. 2016.
- [29] E. Gockenbach and H. Borsi, “Natural and Synthetic Ester Liquids as alternative to mineral oil for power transformers,” in *Annual Report Conference on Electrical Insulation Dielectric Phenomena*, 2008, pp. 521–524.
- [30] Vaisala, “The Effect of Moisture on the Breakdown Voltage of Transformer Oil,” 2011.

Víctor A. Primo was born in Madrid in 1989. In 2014, he obtained a M.Sc. degree in chemistry from Universidad Complutense de Madrid, and in 2015 a M.Sc. degree in materials engineering from Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Spain. Since 2015 he has been a Ph.D. student in the Electrical Engineering Department of Universidad Carlos III de Madrid. His main topic is the development of nanodielectric fluids for electrical applications.

Belén García received the M.Sc. degree in physics from Universidad Complutense de Madrid in 1998, and the Ph.D. degree in electrical engineering from Universidad Carlos III de Madrid in 2002. Since 2004 she has held an Associate Professor position in the Electrical Engineering Dept. of the same university. Her main research interests are power transformer life management and insulating materials.

Juan Carlos Burgos received the PhD degree from the Escuela Técnica Superior de Ingenieros Industriales de Madrid in 1987. Currently, he is an associate professor with the Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Madrid, Spain, where he has worked since 1994. His main research interest area is power transformer maintenance.

Daniel Pérez Rosa was born in Madrid in 1989. In 2014, he obtained a M.Sc. degree in chemistry from Universidad Complutense de Madrid, and in 2015 a M.Sc. degree in materials engineering from Universidad Carlos III de Madrid, Spain. Since 2015 he has been a Ph.D. student in the Electrical Engineering Department of Universidad Carlos III de Madrid. His main topic is the development of nanodielectric fluids for electrical applications.